

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

The use of synthetic images of electrocardiograms (ECGs) and their applications in artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms.

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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(Q1) Proposal name

The use of synthetic images of electrocardiograms (ECGs) and their applications in artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This study uses secondary data to create GenECG, a high-fidelity, synthetic image-based dataset for training AI algorithms.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

This project will generate a quantitative image-based ECG dataset comprising labelled images extracted from clinical ECG recordings. All images will undergo modification to simulate the composition of a real-world image-based ECG dataset.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

This study involves working with secondary data as input. All synthetic image data will be created using a publicly available repository of signal data. The original data is sourced from PTB-XL, the largest freely accessible clinical 12-lead ECG waveform dataset to date, consisting of 21837 records from 18885 patients, each of 10 seconds in length (physionet.org/content/ptb-xl/1.0.0/).

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

A dataset of ~ 21,000 images containing PTB-XL ECGs, incorporating artefacts common to photographed images, will be created and stored in Wave Form Database Format (WFDB), containing two standard categories: MIT Signal files (.dat) MIT Header files (.hea). This format is proposed by PhysioNet (physionet.org/about/software/), which has developed into a de-facto standard for the distribution of physiological signal data.

We estimate that the total file size, including administrative generated data, will be around <300 GB.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Data will be stored securely on local systems, with access restricted to the named research team. The data will be backed up daily using password-protected network storage, which can only be accessed with two-factor authentication. This high-quality, enterprise-class

storage includes guaranteed automatic daily backup and resilience, managed by the IT Infrastructure team. All synthetic ECG image was created according to recommendations outlined in the 'AHA/ACCF/HRS Recommendations for the Standardization and Interpretation of the Electrocardiogram' document ([ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.106.180200](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.106.180200)).

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

The WFDB format does not provide a standardised way of storing signal-specific metadata. For easy accessibility, we will provide the metadata for all data as a table in comma-separated value (csv) format in ptbxl_database.csv, containing 28 columns, which can be easily accessed by using existing libraries in all common programming languages.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

We will keep all important research data, along with the right details about it, for at least 10 years, following the guidelines set by the BBSRC for maintaining high standards in scientific work.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

To ensure long-term accessibility and discoverability of the data, it will be accompanied by comprehensive metadata upon submission. The dataset will be made available on the Hugging Face Hub, a centralised platform for disseminating open machine learning models, datasets, and demonstrations. This will allow individuals, including researchers, to access cutting-edge machine-learning models and datasets with minimal coding requirements.

(Q10) When will data be available?

All the relevant data will be openly available to other researchers in a timely manner, with as few restrictions as possible. We reserve the right not to share data until we have published it and gained the required validation and impact.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

The data will be shared in a repository to ensure it is visible to a wide audience of machine learning researchers. The Hugging Face Hub allows for links between datasets, models, and demos to be exposed, making it easier to see how people are using the datasets

to train models and create demos. Additionally, it will provide a digital object identifier (DOI) that can be used by anyone citing this data in the future.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

To enable easy interpretation of the dataset, it will be thoroughly documented with all necessary information for others to reuse the data. Appropriate metadata will be published with the research data to enable other researchers to identify whether the data could be suitable for their own research.

The code to facilitate batch image generation will be publicly available via a Creative Commons license.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

Apart from the permitted period of exclusive use, there are no restrictions on data sharing.

(Q14) Secondary use

The methodology of this project outlines a framework that other fields can use to generate extensive, realistic synthetic patient datasets, reducing the need to continuously create new patient datasets prospectively.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

All staff and researchers involved in the project are required to complete the relevant Information Security Training and comply with the University's Information Security Policy and Data Protection Policy. Data will be securely stored, with access limited to the research team. The University has ISO 27001 certification.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

The PTB-XL dataset itself is de-identified and anonymous. Therefore, this project will not keep any identifiable data.

(Q17) Capabilities

The university provides strong support for data management through its research data service team, data stewards, and governance team. They help implement effective data management strategies across different projects. No extra costs are anticipated for ongoing access to all data and software beyond those included in the project application.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

The local research data manager and the data stewards team play a crucial role in the initial implementation and ongoing review and revision of the Data Management Plans (DMPs) to ensure that these documents are up-to-date and comprehensive.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

All research staff will undergo training on energy, climate, and biodiversity-related environmental issues. We will share our protocols, research materials such as code, and results in order to contribute to collective work and avoid waste in the form of duplicate efforts.

The University is dedicated to achieving net zero carbon emissions and biodiversity net gain by 2035. It has allocated resources to specialised teams such as the Environmental Sustainability team to assist researchers in their projects.

(Q20) Responsibilities

- **Research Staff:** Every member of the research team is responsible for managing, creating metadata, protecting data, and ensuring the quality of their own data. This personal accountability ensures that data handling practices meet the research project's standards from the ground up.
- **IT team responsibilities:** Ensure the data is properly secured and backed up regularly, in line with PI and the Institute's Data Manager expectations.
- **Metadata Creation:** University Core Facilities, alongside the local data manager and the principal investigator, assist in creating accurate and comprehensive metadata. Peer reviews of metadata standards further enhance the quality and utility of the data.
- **Institutional Training:** The University provides comprehensive training in data management and research practices to all staff. This training is crucial for upholding data integrity and fostering a culture of responsible data handling.
- **Data Managers:** Ensure university data management policy compliance throughout the research life cycle.